

Labelling of Nucleosides with a Fluorescent Dye

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This paper describes a simple, one-step, microscale synthesis of fluorescence labelled nucleosides. Spectroscopic identification of products, optimum conditions for their use and sensitivity of detection are also discussed.

CONSIDERING the immense biochemical importance of nucleosides, it is desirable to detect minute amounts of these molecules by extremely sensitive methods. Fluorescence labelling offers a chemical method for this purpose. The present study is concerned with an easy, fast, one-step microscale synthesis of fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) labelled 2'-deoxyadenosine, guanosine, thymidine, cytidine, and uridine. The labelling agent, FITC, has a readily available highly reactive functional group, the isothiocyanate group, which can react spontaneously with the alcoholic OH or amino groups^{1,2} of the nucleosides. Condensation of isothiocyanate with alcohol or amine produces thiourethan or thiourea^{3,4}.

Direct labelling with a fluorescent dye is much faster compared to the indirect technique⁵. Moreover, high sensitivity of the probes should allow detection of very minute amounts of compounds^{6,7}. In our previous work concerning the labelling of strychnine, the product was contaminated with extensive amounts of phosphates^{8,9}. Although the contamination did not interfere the biochemical use, it is desirable to obtain products free from phosphates. Here, we report a method of fluorescence labelling easy enough to be carried out in a biochemical laboratory.

Experimental

Guanosine, 2'-deoxyadenosine, thymidine, cytidine, uridine and FITC were obtained from Sigma Chemical. Ultraviolet spectra were recorded on a Beckman DU-6 spectrophotometer. Fluorescence was recorded on a Aminco—Bowman spectrofluorometer, and all fluorescences recorded were relative. Infrared spectra (nujol or KBr) were recorded on a Perkin—Elmer 177 grating spectrophotometer. Thin layer chromatography was carried out on silica gel plates using acetone—benzene mixture (1:1, v/v). The developed plates were visualised in uv-light.

Synthesis of FITC labelled nucleosides: Essentially, the nucleoside was added to the slightly alkaline solution of the disodium salt of FITC, both the reactants being taken in equimolecular amounts. A typical synthesis of FITC labelled thymidine is described. Thymidine (20 mg, 82.6 μ mol) was added all at once to a stirred solution of FITC (82 μ mol) in 0.1 M NH_4HCO_3 (20 ml), pH 8.1, in a 100 ml Erlenmeyer flask. The nucleoside slowly went into solution, and the mixture was stirred for 4 h at room temperature to complete the reaction.

Isolation: The reaction mixture was cooled to 0–5° in an ice-bath. To the cold solution, concentrated HCl was carefully added dropwise with stirring till the precipitation was just complete; pH of the final mother liquor being 3. The flask was then kept at 4° overnight to settle the precipitate and then frozen at –20° for 3 days. The frozen mixture was defrosted and filtered cold through a small buchner funnel under water suction. The precipitate was drained, and washed several times carefully with cold distilled water to remove traces of adsorbed HCl. The precipitate was dried under suction for several hours and finally dried over anhydrous calcium chloride in a desiccator for 3 days at room temperature.

Variation of pH: For measurements of fluorescence or absorption of FITC labelled nucleosides at different pH values, the labelled compound (0.1–0.25 mg) was stirred in distilled water (10 ml) for several hours, filtered through filter paper and spectra recorded at pH 7.0. To the solution (3 ml) in the cubette was added 1 N NaOH (3 μ l), mixed and spectra recorded at pH 11.0. Similarly, calculated amount of concentrated HCl was added in the same cubette, mixed and spectra recorded at pH 2.0. The volume changes, being extremely small, were neglected.

Results and Discussion

Yields of the labelled compounds are good (Table 1). The products were identified as follows.

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TABLE 1—YIELDS AND ULTRAVIOLET ABSORPTION OF FITC LABELLED NUCLEOSIDES

Compd. labelled	Yield %	λ_{max} (in water)* nm	λ_{max} of free nucleoside** nm
Thymidine	56	491, 328, (262)*	267
Cytidine	50	493, 234, (275)	271
Uridine	56	492, 235, (266)	261
2'-Deoxyadenosine	67	491, 237, (267)	260
Guanosine	55	494, 237.5	252.5

*Shoulders in parenthesis. **Literature value given for comparison.

(i) FITC has an absorption maximum at 490 nm, and the nucleosides have also characteristic ultraviolet absorptions. Since the product contains both the moieties (Scheme 1), the absorptions due to both fluorescein and nucleoside moieties should

1; X-O
2; X-NH

Scheme 1. Reaction of FITC with alcohol (X-O) and amine (X-NH) to produce thiourea I and thiourea II derivatives, respectively.

be present in the product; this being shown in Table 1. (ii) If the attachment of isothiocyanate occurs to the nitrogen or oxygen of the purine or pyrimidine ring, it should affect the absorption maximum of the nucleoside since the π -electron system is perturbed. The shifts in λ_{max} values (Table 1) are in conformity with expectation. (iii) Isothiocyanate (N=C=S) group has a characteristic ir stretching frequency¹⁰ at $\sim 2025\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Since reaction with OH or NH₂ group produces thiourea or urethan (Scheme 1), this characteristic band should be absent in the labelled nucleoside. Absence of N=C=S frequency confirms the formation of the desired product.

Both absorption maximum and optical density are affected by the change of pH (Table 2). Absorption spectra of neutral and alkaline solutions are more or less similar, with the alkaline solution having little higher optical density. However, in acidic solution, there is a strong blue-shift of about 50 nm and optical density falls dramatically. This effect is due to the phenolic groups present in the fluorescein moiety. Variation of λ_{max} for all the labelled nucleosides are given in Table 2, and the pattern is found to be similar. There is little change in fluorescence from neutral to alkaline solution. However, fluorescence is almost completely

quenched in acidic solution, as shown in Table 2. This effect is also due to the presence of phenolic groups in the fluorescein moiety. It is thus important that neutral or slightly alkaline pH be used for fluorescence measurement. As expected, optical density falls with dilution. However, it is interesting to note that fluorescence increases with dilution.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF pH ON ABSORPTION AND FLUORESCENCE OF LABELLED NUCLEOSIDES

Compd labelled	λ_{max} (nm)* at pH			Fluorescence at pH**		
	7	11	2	7	11	2
2'-Deoxyadenosine	491 (2.01)	492 (2.34)	438 (1.43)	71	55	5
Uridine	492 (1.65)	493.6 (2.09)	440 (1.15)	38.5	26	2
Thymidine	491 (0.84)	493.6 (1.39)	437.2 (0.75)	42	38	2
Cytidine	492.7 (1.37)	493.6 (1.68)	439 (0.85)	39	32	2
Guanosine	494 (0.159)	494 (0.288)	441 (0.124)	40	37	3

*Optical densities in parenthesis. **Excitation at the corresponding λ_{max} value at the given pH, and emission at 520 nm.

At infinite dilution, however, fluorescence decreases with dilution (Fig. 1). The optimum concentration for maximum fluorescence is about $50\ \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$.

Fig. 1. Variation of optical density and fluorescence with concentration.

The sensitivity of detection of the labelled nucleosides has been found to be in the nanomolar range (Fig. 2). A sensitivity of this magnitude should enable their use for biochemical purposes.

In conclusion, the method is fast and simple, gives good yields of products, and can be carried out in microscale. The isolation and spectroscopic identification of products are also straight forward. The labelled compounds should be useful for biochemical purposes, particularly on nucleotide metabolism and nucleic acid synthesis. Labelled

2'-deoxyadenosine is being used in this laboratory for recognition of purine receptors on parasite cell surfaces; preliminary experiment does show the binding of FITC labelled adenosine to the cell

with a fluorescent dye by a simple chemical method. The method should be applicable to nucleotides and nucleic acids which are being labelled in this laboratory.

Fig. 2. Sensitivity of detection of fluorescent nucleosides.

surface of *Leishmania donovani*. This is probably the first report of direct labelling of nucleosides

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